

Outcome:

The HARMLESS ToxFairy software is a novel data management solution for automating high throughput in vitro screening data to increase the efficiency of clustering, ranking, prioritisation and read-across of nanomaterials and advanced materials.

References

To see the full references, scan the QR code:

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HARMLESS

TOXFAIRY

The HARMLESS software solution for automated toxicity scoring and FAIRification of data

Advanced High Aspect Ratio and Multicomponent materials: towards comprehensive intelligent tEsting and Safe by design Strategies

HARMLESS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183.

A data management workflow based on FAIR guiding principles is essential for consistent curation and reusing of large datasets. A novel approach is utilized for *In vitro* high-throughput screening (HTS)-based toxicity assessment, which is used for efficient clustering, ranking, prioritization, and read across of nanomaterials and advanced materials. Nanosafety, cheminformatics, and bioinformatics communities can benefit from this novel data management approach.

Challenges

- ★ Difficulty in consistently assessing and validating multiple agent effects simultaneously in HTS data
- ★ Traditional HTS results documentation approaches, such as using spreadsheets for data collecting and preprocessing are time-consuming and error prone.
- ★ Ensuring data is machine-Readable, Findable, Accessible, and Reusable is complex.

Solutions

ToxFairy Python package for:

- ★ faster HTS data preprocessing
- ★ minimizing possibility of errors
- ★ calculation of toxicological prioritization index
- ★ hierarchical clustering of materials
- ★ making HTS data machine readable based on FAIR principles

Orange3-ToxFairy add-on in Orange data mining as user friendly interface.

★ Custom creation of automatic workflows for fine tuning of data processing.

★ Reusable and shareable automatic workflows with the community.

<https://github.com/ideaconsult/orange3-toxfairy>

Automate and FAIRify your toxicity scoring using TOXFAIRY

Hierarchical clustering and grouping of materials, with optimal cluster numbers and automatically calculated Silhouette, Davies-Bouldin and Calinski-Harabasz cluster significance scores.

Interactive toxicological profiles for each material with toxicity scores. Each slice represents grouped dose-response parameters by cell line, time point and endpoint.

FAIRified HTS data is ready to be uploaded to the eNanoMapper database

Processed and FAIRified HTS data is collected in Nexus file format specialized in handling scientific data. Raw and normalized data as well as dose-response parameters are well-organized as hierarchical structures.